

ATU Research Showcase

Meet ATU's Construction & Infrastructure Experts

Construction & Infrastructure Research with National & International Impact

Ollscoil
Teicneolaíochta
an Atlantaigh

Atlantic
Technological
University

**Research,
Innovation and
Engagement**

This booklet was compiled and designed by the ATU Research Coordinator Team, Dr Alan Naughton, Dr Shane Conway, Dr James Britton and Dr Alan Heron, funded through RISE@ATU.

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**Northern & Western
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The Higher Education Authority

Meet ATU's Construction & Infrastructure Experts

Construction & Infrastructure Research with National & International Impact

To mark Engineers week 2026 (28th February to 6th March), a national initiative which puts a focus on engineering for a full week, the Research Coordinator team at Atlantic Technological University (ATU), funded through RISE@ATU, presents the fourth edition of the ATU Research Showcase Series. This edition highlights the work of ATU researchers whose work focuses on current and future construction and infrastructure needs.

Aligning with Engineers week while also putting a spotlight on an area of key national importance - construction and infrastructure engineering is the theme of this showcase. From housing delivery and road network improvements to electric vehicle infrastructure and sustainable development there is a broad area where innovative research can shape future developments.

As the technological university for the West and North-West, ATU grounds its engineering research in regional, national and international priorities. In alignment with Ireland's National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) for Innovation 2022–2027. It reflects interdisciplinary research and collaboration across ATU's faculties and Research Centres.

This booklet presents a representative sample of 12 researchers whose profiles demonstrate ATU's growing expertise in construction and infrastructure research that can contribute to both national and international developments. Many other colleagues across ATU are making equally valuable contributions in both this field and other areas of engineering, and this Showcase is intended to reflect a cross-section of that collective strength rather than provide an exhaustive account.

Profiled ATU Researchers

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ATU

ATU Campus Locations

Engineers

ATU Research Showcase Engineers Week 2026

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Education & Infrastructure Experts

Research with National & International Impact

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Week

Dr Amaya Vega

Evidence-based transport policy for sustainable regional mobility

ATU Galway

Dr Amaya Vega is a senior lecturer in economics at ATU. Her research interests are in transport policy evaluation and demand analysis. Central to her research is the analysis of human decisions using advanced discrete choice models.

She leads the transport research stream of the Atlantic Futures project funded under the North-South Research Programme, working closely with local authorities, national policymakers, transport operators and communities to assess mode and route choice and their impact on regional competitiveness.

Dr Vega is Principal Investigator on the EMBRACE project under the Research Ireland National Challenge Fund, developing decision-support tools for rural road network management and community resilience, and on the ROBUST project funded by the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland, trialling electric shared mobility hubs in four Irish cities. She also co-leads the ATU IDEAS Postgraduate Research Training Programme and supervises six PhD students in transport, supply chain management and regional economics.

Dr Trevor McSharry

Advancing sustainable infrastructure through innovation, digitalisation and industry-engaged engineering research

ATU Sligo

Dr Trevor McSharry is the Head of School of the Built Environment at ATU and a researcher at ATU Sligo. Dr McSharry's research focuses on strengthening Ireland's current and future infrastructure through innovation and digital transformation. With extensive experience across construction management, engineering, sustainability and digital adoption, Trevor leads and supports applied research collaborations that address national priorities such as housing delivery, modern construction methods, lean project delivery, BIM capability, infrastructure productivity and workforce development.

Dr McSharry's work spans the development of new digital tools, sector wide capability frameworks, bespoke industry education solutions, and funded research partnerships that enhance resilience, efficiency and sustainability across infrastructure systems. By combining engineering expertise with strategic leadership and strong industry engagement, Trevor contributes to creating a more sustainable, connected and future ready built environment.

Dr Conan O'Ceallaigh

Biobased and sustainable solutions for the built environment

ATU Galway

Dr Conan O'Ceallaigh is a Principal Investigator, lecturer and Chartered Engineer in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering at ATU Galway. Conan obtained his PhD by examining the long-term performance of timber structures and is involved in leading research on National and European-funded projects focused on increasing the use of timber in construction, developing sustainable engineered wood products, quantifying the life cycle impacts and particularly the embodied carbon associated with construction, and decarbonising the built environment by implementing circular principles during the design stage.

Dr O'Ceallaigh is also a management committee member of COST Action: CA20139: Holistic Design of Taller Timber Buildings to provide more prescriptive rules governing the design of mass-timber elements in multi-story timber construction and is currently PI for a Construct Innovate funded project on the structural health monitoring of a mass timber structure in Ireland.

Dr Jan Götsche

Advancing sustainability and circularity in the built environment

ATU Galway

Dr. Jan Götsche is a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Building & Civil Engineering at ATU Galway. He holds a BSc., MSc., MA and PhD from ATU and is actively engaged in applied research with multinational and SME contractors across the Irish construction sector.

Dr Götsche's work focuses on sustainability, resource efficiency, construction and demolition waste management, the circular economy, and education for sustainability. A key strand of his research examines how sustainability education influences third-level learners, including use of the New Ecological Paradigm scale to track environmental attitudes.

He contributes to the national Build360 Hub supporting Ireland's transition to a decarbonised and circular construction industry and to Building a Circular Ireland, a roadmap developed with the IGBC. Dr Götsche is a Fellow of the Higher Education Academy, supervises undergraduate and postgraduate students and has published widely in conference proceedings and peer-reviewed academic journals.

Dr Brian McCann

Sustainable performance indicator systems for transport and wastewater infrastructure

ATU Sligo

Dr Brian McCann is a lecturer and Principal Investigator in Civil Engineering in the Department of Civil Engineering & Construction at ATU Sligo. He is also the Programme Chair for Master of Engineering in Road and Transport Engineering

Dr McCann's ongoing research projects include: The development of sustainable optimisation indicator systems for small to medium activated sludge wastewater treatment plants in Ireland;

Analysis of "First and Last Green Mile" sustainable transport modes, infrastructure and services in County Leitrim to encourage modal shift from private car to active, mass-transit and low-carbon alternatives for residents in rural locations;

International freight connectivity in the North-West of Ireland and its implications for regional competitiveness. Research Stream 6 - HEA North-South Research Programme - Atlantic Futures (ATU/UU/UL/UoG) collaborative project. It examines the effect of connectivity/route infrastructure, freight decarbonisation, travel mode/fuels shift to more sustainable forms - rail, EVs and HVO;

SEAI National Energy Research RD&D Programme - ROBUST - Electric shared mobility hubs trial in collaboration with TCD and industrial partners ESB and Enterprise Mobility

Christoph Schellenberg

*Computational intelligence for smart heat pumps
in smart energy systems*

ATU Galway

Christoph Schellenberg is a lecturer in the Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering at ATU Galway. Advancing sustainable infrastructure begins with smarter energy systems, which is the core focus of his research.

As a member of ATU's integrated Sustainable Energy Technologies (iSET) research group, he applies computational intelligence techniques, including predictive analytics and metaheuristic optimisation algorithms, to holistically improve the interaction of heat pumps with national grid systems.

This innovation supports decarbonisation, emissions reduction, and energy security, central to Ireland's housing, transport, and renewable infrastructure goals. It contributes to national and international efforts to build a low-carbon, energy-secure future.

Dr Shane Newell

Engineering a sustainable built environment

ATU Sligo

Dr Shane Newell is Head of Department and researcher in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering at ATU Galway. He is a Chartered Engineer with over twenty years of experience in engineering consultancy and technical advice to the construction industry. His research interests include structural health monitoring, innovative construction materials, sustainable design and circular economy in the built environment.

Dr Newell's research has a strong applied industry focus and he has collaborated with indigenous and international organisations on research projects which enhance delivery of infrastructure leading to more resilient and sustainable development.

He is a member of the ATU Build360 research group which works in close collaboration with the public and private sector focusing on applied research in built environment decarbonisation, circularity and regeneration. His research aims to deliver practical engineering solutions which will deliver a more sustainable built environment sector.

Dr Irene Hayden

Building regulation compliance and visual building regulation pedagogical research

ATU Galway

Dr Irene Hayden is a lecturer in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering and a member of the Engineering Research Group at ATU Galway.

Dr Hayden's research on the MSc Built Environment Regulation has evolved from her PhD thesis entitled "Online visual pedagogy for building regulation competencies: experiences and perceptions of professional development stakeholders and the wider context", and winning the Taylor & Francis Award for Best Paper presented by Architectural Engineering and Design Management Journal at the 7th ICAT Conference, entitled "An evaluation of the design and use of applied visual interactive resources for teaching building regulations in higher education built environment programmes".

Dr Hayden's supervision of masters students on this programme has specialised in indoor air quality and radon mitigation in dwellings and schools, EV infrastructural feasibility to meet large organisational sustainability goals, fire and UD in the context of access and egress for private dwellings, Approved Housing Bodies, Local Authorities, and Multi-Unit Developments, and the philosophy of workmanship and its prescribed compliance protocols in built environment regulation research.

Dr Alan Duggan

Advancing ground improvement and sustainable civil engineering solutions

ATU Galway

Dr Alan Duggan is a lecturer in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering at ATU Galway. He is also a chartered Civil Engineer with over 14 years' experience in research, higher education, and design consultancy. He completed a PhD in Geotechnical Engineering.

Dr Duggan has extensive experience in geotechnical and civil engineering, covering earthworks, foundations, soft ground engineering, peat stabilisation and temporary works design. His research interests include ground improvement and soft ground engineering, sustainable development and life cycle assessment, carbon capture and carbonation processes, groundwater modelling, slope stability, and structural engineering for heavy civil works.

Current research includes a TII-funded project developing technical guidance on reusing surplus peat from road schemes to restore degraded peatlands and enhance biodiversity habitats.

Dr David Collery

3D concrete printing - Sustainable concrete

ATU Sligo

Dr David Collery is a lecturer in the Department of Civil Engineering and Construction at ATU Sligo and a researcher in the Centre for Environmental Research, Innovation and Sustainability (CERIS). Dr Collery's research in collaboration with Dr Tomás O'Flaherty centres around automation in construction and the use of 3D printed concrete (3DPC). 3DPC can reduce construction time by up to 30% and use less material than conventional formwork construction.

The majority of existing 3DPC research relies on mortar mixes (limited aggregates) because coarse aggregates are difficult to extrude (print). This limits 3DPC strength and increases cement demand, cost, and carbon emissions. Dr Collery's research aims to develop a sustainable Irish 3DPC mix with reduced cement content by studying additives and local aggregates, including sizes above the typical 5 mm limit currently used in most 3DPC.

Optimising printability, mechanical performance and environmental impact will bridge the gap between the printing technology and material science to make 3DPC a reality in everyday construction.

Daniel Clarke Hagan

Responsible construction and project delivery

ATU Sligo

Daniel Clarke Hagan is a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering at ATU-Sligo. He is also a Fellow of the Higher Education Academy. Prior to entering academia, he spent many years in the Construction Industry across Ireland, Northern Ireland and the UK and is currently Program Director for the Construction and Project Management courses at ATU Sligo. Daniel is also a coordinating judge for the Irish Construction Industry awards, a Judge for the Irish Engineering Excellence awards and a member of the Association of Researchers in Construction Management (ARCOM) scientific committee.

Daniel has delivered guest lectures in Universities and Colleges across Ireland and the UK, presented to Industry and at conferences, with many papers published on factors affecting the construction industry.

His research interests include BIM and AI, Lean Construction, Smart buildings, Big Data and IOT, Blockchain, corporate social responsibility in construction, improving workforce wellbeing, and exploring progressive work practices. Through applied research and industry partnership, Daniel contributes to shaping a more collaborative, sustainable, and people-centred built environment.

Dr Yadong Jiang

Enhancing composite bondline strength with T-Bolts

ATU Galway

Dr Yadong Jiang is a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering at ATU Galway. During his PhD in Earthquake Engineering at IUSS and the University of Pavia he investigated the seismic performance of concrete-filled steel tube (CFST) structures, combining experimental testing and numerical analysis. His research interests include Earthquake Engineering, Renewable Energy, Composite Materials and Energy Conversion Devices. As a recipient of the 2020 SFI Industrial Fellowship, Dr Jiang conducted research as a PI within an industrial company developing a novel methodology for retrofitting end-of-life turbines with high-efficiency rotor blades.

Prior to joining ATU Dr Jiang led structural testing in the SEAI-funded project “FASTSHIP - Development and testing of a novel technology to facilitate faster, cleaner, cheaper shipping (22/RDD/876)”, which develops faster, cleaner and cheaper composite bow-foil technology for shipping. Two 2 m glass fibre, epoxy I-beams, with and without T-bolts, were tested to failure. T-bolts improved load transfer, prevented web failure, and reduced crack growth, significantly enhancing bondline strength and reliability for hydrofoil applications.

Irish Wood and Interiors Network (IWIN) ATU Industry Cluster

ATU hosts four Enterprise Ireland-funded industry clusters that play an important role in supporting regional innovation, productivity and enterprise growth. Collectively, these clusters engage with over 100 companies across manufacturing and related sectors, providing platforms for collaboration in skills development, technology adoption, innovation, market development and shared infrastructure across the west and north-west of Ireland. One such cluster at ATU is the Irish Wood and Interiors Network (IWIN), which supports companies involved in the design and manufacture of kitchens, architectural joinery, contract furniture, bespoke interior solutions, commercial interiors and a wide range of wood-based products and services.

IWIN's activity is structured around three core pillars: Advanced Manufacturing, Business Development, and Collaboration. Through these pillars, the cluster supports companies to improve productivity, adopt lean and sustainable manufacturing practices, engage with digitalisation and smart industry technologies, and identify new domestic and international market opportunities. Collaboration and peer-to-peer learning are central to the network's approach, recognising the value of shared experience and collective problem-solving within the sector.

Importantly, this ATU industry cluster acts as a key interface between industry, applied research, education and state bodies, supporting the translation of research expertise into manufacturing practice and innovation. Cluster activities include lean and sustainability consulting, digital and AI readiness supports, factory tours, international trade missions, supply-chain collaboration, skills development and engagement with higher education institutions. Through this applied, industry-led model, the Irish Wood and Interiors Network (IWIN) contributes to strengthening innovation capacity, competitiveness and long-term resilience within Ireland's interiors and wood-based manufacturing sector.

ATU Construction Management Annual Conference

For over a decade, the ATU Construction Management Annual Conference has been a cornerstone event for construction professionals and academics, running successfully for 12 years at ATU Galway before finding a new and equally vibrant home in ATU Sligo. Its continued growth reflects the strength of collaboration between industry and education, and a shared commitment to advancing standards across the built environment.

As one of the few large-scale industry–academic events of its kind in the West and North-West of Ireland, it provides a vital platform for knowledge exchange, innovation, and professional networking. The conference benefits from strong collaboration with, and support from, leading professional bodies including the Society of Chartered Surveyors Ireland (SCSI), Chartered Institute of Building (CIOB), Chartered Institute of Architectural Technologists (CIAT), and the Construction Industry Federation (CIF).

Lisa Brennan, Chair of the ATU Annual International Construction Management Conference, explains that ‘this Conference not only showcases cutting-edge research and industry best practice but also delivers meaningful economic and professional benefits to the region, strengthening regional partnerships, supporting local enterprise, and inspiring the next generation of construction leaders’.

The upcoming 15th ATU Construction Management Conference, taking place on March 5th 2026 at ATU Sligo, will provide a forum for engagement between industry, academia and students, with presentations focusing on current issues, projects and developments within the construction sector.

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